

War Decisions Under Risk Asymmetry: Why Deterrence Breaks Down

Series IV: Decision-Making and Security Architecture
Working Paper No. 1

Work in Progress — April 2026

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Abstract

The paper analyzes the paradox of asymmetry in the perception of risk and its influence on decision-making on military aggression. It is shown that decision-makers demonstrate stable risk aversion in the domain of gains and a tendency toward risk in the domain of losses, which is confirmed by the results of behavioral economics and prospect theory.

Under conditions in which maintaining peaceful behavior is associated with current and personalized losses for a political leader, while the possible negative consequences of aggression have a probabilistic and delayed nature, a systemic bias arises in favor of risky decisions, including military actions.

An extended model of expected utility is proposed, which includes, in addition to the magnitude of consequences and the probability of their occurrence, a time factor interpreted through a discount coefficient. On this basis, the principle of temporal-probabilistic asymmetry of aggression is formulated, and the insufficiency of deterrence systems based exclusively on the threat of losses is shown.

The key conclusion is that for the sustainable prevention of aggression, the institutionalization of a guaranteed gain from peaceful behavior is necessary. Such a construction complements the system of economic security guarantees and makes it possible to transform the structure of incentives, making peace a rationally preferable choice.

Keywords

risk asymmetry; decision-making; prospect theory; military aggression; deterrence; economic security guarantees; discounting; political leadership; behavioral economics; international security

JEL Classification

F51 — International Conflicts; Negotiations; Sanctions

F52 — National Security; Economic Nationalism

K33 — International Law

G10 — General Financial Markets

1. Introduction

Decisions on the initiation of military actions are traditionally analyzed within the framework of the concept of rational choice, where a comparison of expected benefits and costs is assumed. However, empirical observations and behavioral studies show that real decisions systematically deviate from this model. It has been proven and repeatedly confirmed that decision-makers demonstrate a stable asymmetry in the perception of gains and losses, as well as probabilities of their occurrence.

At the same time, it is important that the decision is made not by an abstract state, but by a specific person (group), and the distribution of expected gains and losses has a personalized character.

This asymmetry acquires critical importance in situations of political instability, when a state leader finds himself in the domain of inevitable losses. This behavioral feature creates a systemic bias toward risky decisions, including military actions, and existing deterrence mechanisms based on punishment are insufficient.

The thesis is introduced about the necessity of the institutional creation of a guaranteed gain from peaceful behavior as a missing element of the system of economic security guarantees.

This preprint does not set the task of constructing an exhaustive theory of political choice. Its task is narrower: to show that in the analysis of decisions on aggression, the basic model of expected utility must be expanded through the introduction of controllable variables—time, probability, and the scale of events, forming a system of targeted influences on the decision-making process.

The key thesis of the work is as follows:

a deterrence system based only on the threat of losses remains incomplete; to complete it, it is necessary to institutionally introduce a guaranteed gain from peaceful behavior, taking into account the personalization of gains and losses for decision-makers.

2. Decision-Making Paradox — Gains, Losses, and Time

A well-known and described situation involves two lotteries with equivalent expected values. The gain lottery is as follows: either +10,000 USD with probability 1, or +1,000,000 USD with probability 0.01. From the standpoint of expected utility, these options are equivalent. However, in real decision-making situations, decision-makers

overwhelmingly choose the guaranteed gain. Preference is given to a smaller but strictly certain result.

The opposite pattern is observed in the domain of losses, i.e., in lotteries with losing outcomes: a guaranteed loss of 10,000 USD with probability 1.0, or a possible loss of 1,000,000 USD with probability 0.01. Here, the majority of decision-makers prefer the risky option, ignoring the small probability of a catastrophic outcome.

This asymmetry is confirmed by simple experiments. For example, the author, in work with first-year students, offered a choice: to receive immediate exemption for one month from tuition payment (100 USD), or to attempt to draw a card (the ace of hearts) from a deck (36 cards) with a chance to receive exemption from payment for the entire three-year course (3,600 USD). Despite arithmetic equivalence, almost all chose the guaranteed option (100 USD guaranteed and immediately).

In the reverse formulation — to pay a small amount now or to accept the risk of significantly larger losses — most prefer the risky option, perceiving the probability of $1/36$ as negligibly small.

Simple but non-trivial conclusions from these and similar experiments consist in the fact that decision-makers demonstrate risk aversion in the domain of gains and a tendency toward risk in the domain of losses (Allais, 1953; Kahneman & Tversky, 1992).

In this work, to these well-known effects of economic behavior we add the factor of time: the remoteness of consequences additionally reduces their subjective significance. The attractiveness of large gains and the catastrophic nature of large losses are psychologically reduced twice — besides small probabilities, the decision-making process also includes the procedure of evaluating future results at the moment of decision-making (the discounting procedure).

The application of discount coefficients to expected outcomes confirms that the choice of guaranteed and small but immediate gains is rationally reinforced.

A stronger logic operates in the domain of losses: the remoteness of negative consequences additionally reduces their subjective significance. Thus, for the decision-maker, in addition to probability — which he may neglect (which is in fact a belief in the non-obligatory nature of the execution of threats of punishment) — there is also the remoteness of negative consequences, which are devalued and perceived as something not very serious.

Thus, we are not speaking about random deviations from rationality, but about a systematic and predictable shift toward risky decisions in conditions of losses. This shift is a structural property of the decision-making process and must be considered as an object of regulation.

3. Decision-Making on War: Focus on the Leader and Personal Risks

Let us consider a situation in which a political leader is faced with the necessity of making a decision on the initiation of military aggression.

We note that here not only a specific person (the head of state) may appear, but also a small group of persons with “special interests.” Without loss of generality, we will further use the term “leader.”

Let us consider a situation in which, under the preservation of peaceful behavior, the outcome for the leader is associated with personal, current, and immediate threats (loss of control, position, assets, political and social status, possible prosecution and personal sanctions against the immediate circle...). Here, the leader finds himself in a domain where, as is known, risk-seeking dominates and behaves as a typical agent in such conditions, i.e., demonstrates a tendency to accept the risk of a low-probability and temporally distant catastrophe in order to avoid a personal inevitable loss (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979; Bueno de Mesquita et al., 2003).

For the leader, the structure of outcomes is simple: peace (personal losses with high probability in the near future) or war (a low-probability catastrophe, moreover temporally distant).

At the same time, incoming information is distorted by loyal associates and compliant officials in such a way that:

- a) immediate and current losses are overestimated;
- b) the probability of a large military gain is overestimated;
- c) delayed losses are underestimated;
- d) military, political, and economic threats are undefined and underestimated.

Small probabilities can be neglected altogether.

Then the decision on military actions becomes possible and illusorily rational, and the risk of catastrophe of the country may be perceived by the leadership of the state as an acceptable (the only?) way to avoid a personal guaranteed loss.

4. Basic and Extended Models

Let's turn to theory. According to the classical Bernoulli formula, expected utility is defined as:

$$P = V \cdot p,$$

where V is the magnitude of the expected gain/loss, and p is the probability of its occurrence.

Expected utility theory (Bernoulli, D. (1738/1954); von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944) and its numerous generalizations and refinements retain the basic property: expected utility is a function of the magnitude of the gain/loss V and the probability p . Behavioral effects were demonstrated in the experimental work of Allais (1953), received a theoretical explanation within the framework of prospect theory (Kahneman and Tversky, 1979), and have been confirmed by models of choice (Bordalo, Gennaioli, Shleifer, 2012).

Our interpretation presents a somewhat more complex picture: in addition to the expected benefit and expected probability, we introduce the expected time (t) of its realization into the basic formula, namely:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{V} \cdot \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{k}(t) \quad (*)$$

where $k(t)$ is the discount factor.

Or, more generally:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{p}, \mathbf{t}),$$

where F is non-decreasing in V and p and non-increasing over time.

Here, time acts as an indicator of the "unattractiveness" of the expected benefit (Frederick, Loewenstein & O'Donoghue, 2002; Rozenfeld, 2007).

We use this formula as an extended three-parameter utility model; it incorporates the idea of "discounting utility."

Corollary 1: A guaranteed outcome is expected in full and immediately;

Corollary 2: A negative outcome is expected with low probability in some distant future.

In connection with our main topic of preventing military conflicts, we utilize the well-known effect of prospect theory and formulate it as a principle of the temporal probabilistic asymmetry of military aggression:

"in the domain of expected benefits, risk aversion predominates, whereas in the domain of expected losses, war risk acceptance predominates."

5. Control Model

From this perspective, the decision-making process can be modeled as a three-parameter control object (**V-p-t control model**), and the outcome itself as a function of three main variables: the magnitude of the consequence (V), the probability (p), and time (t).

An effective deterrence system should simultaneously influence all parameters:

- 1) change the magnitude of gains and losses (both large and small), i.e., change the magnitude of expected consequences and increase responsibility for the decision;
- 2) increase (or even guarantee) the probability of an event, transforming possible negative consequences into automatic, deterministic, and guaranteed causal losses;
- 3) bring the event closer or further away, i.e., increase (or decrease) its value discounted to the time of decision-making.

The proposed system of economic security guarantees (SEG) satisfies these requirements and ensures (Rosenfeld, 2024, 2026):

- 1) guaranteed immediate and automatic punishment of the aggressor;
- 2) guaranteed immediate payments to support the victim of aggression;
- 3) activation of internal resistance processes;
- 4) personal sanctions against decision-makers;
- 5) punishment of the aggressor country in the post-war period;

This set of predetermined measures influences decision-making in the following ways:

- determines the expected scale of major losses, including sanctions, asset seizures, and other personal consequences for decision-makers;
- supports the victim of aggression, i.e., reduces the likelihood of military success, increases defensive capabilities, and thus complicates the achievement of military goals and delays the expected benefits of quick victories;
- activates internal resistance, i.e., increases the current costs of waging war.

Given that the absolute values of fines and support in the economic guarantee system are known in advance, these measures can be interpreted as a control system that, in the expanded formula (*), simultaneously:

- increases V (losses as the cost of violation),
- increases p (the expected probability of punishment shifts toward inevitability),
- minimizes $k(t)$ (approaching potential losses over time and delaying potential benefits).

Thus, the use of an economic guarantee system influences both the processes and outcomes of decision-making.

6. Insufficiency of the Existing Security System

An important remark. In the domain of gains, the leader has no lottery at all. A major military victory (even with a small probability) is contrasted only with the reality of the current situation, which is unsatisfactory (otherwise the idea of radical action would not arise at all).

Thus, even with a substantial reduction in the probability of military success, this success is compared with the real alternative of a peaceful solution, which in many cases has almost zero subjective expected utility for the leader (decision-maker).

In other words, war is perceived as a lottery with a possible large gain, while peace remains a state without significant personal gain and is associated only with current losses.

This approach explains why military decisions are made at all; it shows why threats of punishment and condemnation do not fully work, i.e., do not stop aggressors.

If peace is associated only with losses, then even a low-probability success of war may be perceived as preferable.

As a result, threats of punishment only reduce the attractiveness of aggression but do not prevent it.

If peace does not provide positive expected utility for decision-makers, then even in the presence of threats of punishment, military aggression remains a rationally permissible strategy.

7. The Necessity of Rewarding Peace

From the aforementioned principle of asymmetry, it follows that in the sphere of benefits, a smaller but guaranteed positive outcome is preferable.

If this effect extends to international security, then neutralizing the temptation to war does not necessarily require promising a potential aggressor enormous benefits from peace. It is sufficient that the current benefit from peace be certain and guaranteed, thereby reducing and neutralizing the subjective attractiveness of military strategies.

In terms of the actual goals of prevention, this is not about compensation or concessions to a potential aggressor, but rather about structurally transforming the utility function, constructing an alternative lottery, and shifting decision-making to the sphere of benefits.

Thus, economic guarantees of peace are complete if and only if they simultaneously:

- 1) reduce the subjective expected utility of the benefits of aggression and shift them further into the future;
- 2) increase the scale and probability of large losses in the event of aggression and bring the negative consequences closer in time;
- 3) Guarantee real benefits in the event of a military solution being abandoned.

Without any of these elements, the system remains unstable.

Key takeaway:

To prevent war, it is not enough to increase the aggressor's expected losses and reduce the probability of success; it is also necessary to ensure guaranteed benefits from peaceful behavior.

8. Conclusion

Economic guarantees of security of the first level (sanctions, support of the victim, increase of costs) reduce the attractiveness of aggression but do not eliminate it completely.

A complete system requires the addition of a second level — a guaranteed reward for peace. This transforms the strategic structure of international interaction and makes possible a stable and regulated political equilibrium.

Decisions about war become irrational, and peace arises as a result of an equilibrium of incentives.

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